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Metabolic derangement in active CD.

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- HK3 induction
- Idh2 induction
- Hcar2/3 induction
- Pfkfb3 induction

Citations

1. Yang, Z., Goronzy, J.J. and Weyand, C.M., 2014. The glycolytic enzyme PFKFB3/phosphofructokinase regulates autophagy. *Autophagy*, 10(2), pp.382-383.